

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS BY TASK BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING

Otaboyeva Naimaxon Narimon qizi

Master's student of NamSU

Abstract: This study aims to develop the students' speaking skills. The initial data showed the students' problems in speaking due to inadequate knowledge of language: grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, fluency, and comprehension. They were not familiar with different communicative tasks. This concern led to a study design as an action research through three cycles conducted in one semester course employing task-based learning.

Keywords: Speaking skills, Task-based learning, Learning

Speaking as one of the four skills is perceived as the most prominent. It has been an ultimate goal of language learning. People who know a language are referred to as 'speaker' of that language, as if speaking included all other kinds of knowing. These people employ their linguistics knowledge and non-linguistics knowledge at ease when speaking. They negotiate meaning, convey objection, negate arguments, and explore ideas in an interaction. However, in the case of students learning another language, the situation might be in the contrary since they do not have sufficient knowledge of language to convey the ideas. To be able to speak fluently postulates not only knowledge of language feature, but also ability to process information and language at the time the speakers are demonstrating the skill. The features of language such as grammar and vocabulary support meaning. The use of appropriate sentence structure helps the students understand and respond the message transferred.

The communication will keep on going if the students use their sufficient knowledge of vocabulary and their background knowledge of the topic being said.

They can develop the topic into many different fields. The students will produce proper pronunciation if they can notice the rules of how to sound the language, for instance, an English word has two syllables, the stress is usually on the first syllable for nouns and adjectives, and the second syllables for verbs. In other words, to be able to speak fluently is not easy. Implementation to improve the students speaking skills have shown the benefits. The findings of a study conducted by Jenefer Philp, Susan Walter and Basturkmen reveals that the task and social consideration effect the students' motivation to cope with the difficulties of language form during peer task-based interaction. This could occur since the students have a chance to do negotiation of form during the interaction. Negotiation in interaction promotes comprehension. Negotiation of form is oriented toward resolving linguistic problem in which the

students and their interlocutors attempt to improve linguistic accuracy in students' speech even when there is no communication breakdown between them, while negotiation of meaning is oriented toward resolving communication problems. Palma carried out a research on negotiation of meaning to seek the interactional adjustment produced by English students and found participants conducting significant amount of meaning and negotiation and producing modified output. The findings of two researches above indicate that assigning students to participate in different tasks challenges them to maintain and to evaluate their learning process. The more frequent the students participate in different tasks, the better they evaluate their own performance.

The difference of this study compared to the previous studies mentioned above is that this study aims to develop students' speaking skills of the fifth aspects: grammar, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension, and pronunciation. The students were provided with tasks that require them to negotiate in both form and meaning since they have problems with the language aspects. The researcher adopts action research method (CAR) through three cycles conducted in one semester course employing task-based learning. arrive at an outcome from given information through process of thought, and which allow teacher to control and to regulate that process. Task is crucial for performance. The students will have no idea whether they have problems with their language performance without completing the tasks. To solve the problems, lecturers teaching students in higher

education level can adopt task-based learning since this approach relies heavily on a sequence of tasks during the a lesson.

In TBL or Task-Based Learning perspective, task provides focus and context for learning, and the students are motivated to use language while completing the tasks . As the progress of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), TBL extends its focus on both form and communication. The students are stimulated to prioritize a focus on meaning more than on form of language and it is not necessarily to be well-formed in order to be meaningful. Specific vocabulary and grammar can be reviewed as target language for raising students' consciousness of their linguistic knowledge. The complete task-based implementation follows certain phases which are pre-task, during the task, and post-task. The first phase is pre-task in which the lecturer introduces the topic and gives the students instructions for completing the tasks. The lecturer reviews some language that will be used during completing the tasks. This phase is followed by 'during the task' in which the students increase their part in learning. The role of the lecturer shifts from an instructor to a facilitator. The students sit as in pairs or groups and helps them in negotiating the words or phrase, grammar, and pronunciation. The students may practice small dialogs or short role play using the language. The third phase is 'post-task' in which the students report to the whole

class in the form of discussion. The lecturer as the advisor gives feedback on form or word meaning from context. The lecturer may ask the students to repeat or develop the previous task.

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